

Porosity Prediction in Selective Laser Melting Combining Photodiode-based In-Process Monitoring and X-CT

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Abstract

Laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) currently faces challenges in consistency, complexity, and cost associated with quality assurance. In-situ process monitoring is a potential approach to this problem. This work investigates the feasibility of using photodiodes for quality monitoring and correlates photodiode signals with X-ray computed tomography (X-CT) based on deep learning. A cube of Ti-6Al-4V grade 23 was produced with optimum energy density parameters. Porosity was analyzed using X-CT to help understand the size, shape, location, and the number of pores formed. The photodiode signals were recorded using the coaxial melt-pool monitoring system on an in-house developed LPBF machine. The photodiode signals collected during processing were segmented per layer accordingly using different window sizes. The classifiers were trained to predict the presence and location of porosities considering the inter-hatch effect. Moreover, different models were trained and compared, which will act as a baseline for further research. The results showed that using photodiode signals can yield a prediction sensitivity of 68% and an accuracy of 84% for pores with a cross-section larger than 100 μm^2 , with an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) of 0.86. These findings suggest that photodiodes can be a promising approach to quality monitoring in LPBF with sub-layer spatial resolution.

Keywords: In-process monitoring, X-ray computed tomography, Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF), Machine learning (ML)

1 Introduction

Metal additive manufacturing (AM), also known as metal 3D printing, is a promising advanced manufacturing technology that involves the use of high-energy beams (such as lasers, electron beams, or arcs) to melt and fuse metal powders or wire layer by layer to create complex and customized metal components. This technology is gaining widespread attention due to its many advantages, such as efficient material usage, producing highly customized parts, and improved engineering performance. For example, G.E. has used metal AM to print aero engine fuel nozzles, which were traditionally made by joining several small components. By printing the nozzles in one piece, their reliability and safety in operation are improved. Additionally, the flexibility of metal AM enables faster industrial reconversion, enhancing the resilience of companies in the face of market changes or other unpredictable events. The market for AM is expected to grow significantly, with revenue coming from various sectors, including medical, aerospace, automotive, and gas turbine, among others.

This research uses LPBF, a type of metal AM technology that involves the use of a laser beam to selectively melt and fuse layers of metal powder according to a computer-aided design (CAD) model. The process begins by spreading a layer of metal powder on a building platform, and then using a laser beam to melt and fuse the powder according to the CAD model. This process is repeated layer by layer until the entire desired geometry is built up, resulting in a fully consolidated metal part. In LPBF, the feedstock material is in the form of metal powder, and the laser beam is used to melt and fuse the powder in the powder bed to create the cross-sectional area of the part [1].

Despite the many benefits of metal LPBF, it is often prone to the formation of defects such as lack-of-fusion (LoF) voids, gas-trapped pores (GEP), keyholes, residual stress, cracking, and poor surface roughness. Some of these are caused by insufficient melting of the metal powder, while the other defects are due to high energy density input. These defects can be caused by various non-ideal factors, including hardware and material behavior, consolidation issues, material evaporation, and laser acceleration. The melt pool, which is the molten metal surrounding the laser-material interaction zone, is a key factor in the formation of defects. The melt pool's morphology and thermal distribution can impact the part's final microstructure and quality [2]. Inhomogeneities in the melt pool intensity and geometry can be caused by the dynamics of the laser scanner and heat absorption and transfer during the LPBF process. These defects can be significant in size and can have an irregular shape, making them particularly problematic in applications where fatigue resistance is important, especially those subjected to repetitive and large mechanical loads, such as in the aerospace and biomedical industries. To improve the reliability of LPBF, there is an urgent need for metrology solutions that can provide non-destructive and comprehensive post-process evaluations of LPBF parts, including dimensional and geometrical measurements and analysis of these defects. Besides, the coupling between the various factors that

can contribute to defect formation in LPBF makes it challenging to model and predict defects, highlighting the importance of effective in-process and post-process evaluation methods.

The aim of this study is to investigate internal porosity defects, including loss of fusion (LoF), gas entrapment pores (GEP), and keyholes. X-CT is a promising technique for evaluating LPBF parts non-destructively and comprehensively. By analyzing the relationship between X-CT results and specific process dynamics signals, it is possible to gain a deeper understanding of the LPBF process and implement corrective actions to prevent future process anomalies and product failures or rejections due to unacceptable defect rates or geometric inaccuracies. One potential approach to achieving this goal is developing an in-situ and in-process monitoring system and feedback control process parameters [3]. This approach involves establishing a relationship between X-CT post-process measurements and in-process data on phenomena and anomalies occurring during the LPBF process through either physics-driven or data-driven methods, or a combination of both. This relationship aims to improve understanding of the LPBF process and validate data acquired at different resolutions, enabling the implementation of a feedback control loop that can take corrective actions during the process to improve manufacturing outcomes. The ultimate goal is to produce zero-defect parts in a one-go way.

There have been numerous in-process monitoring systems proposed in the literature for metal LPBF, which gathers information from different stages of the process, such as the powder bed, scan tracks, or melt pool, and from different parameters settings, such as high-energy density input/optimal/low-energy density input [4–6]. Scime and Beuth [7] used an optical camera to capture powder bed images and applied computer vision algorithms to detect powder bed defects, achieving an accuracy of 65% to 99% for different defects using the "bag-of-words" algorithm and an accuracy of 72.7% using a multi-scale convolutional neural network (CNN) [8]. Photodiodes, which have a sufficiently high sampling frequency for capturing the complex phenomena in the melt pool, are another type of sensor that is economically viable for mass implementation [9]. Taherkhani et al. [10] used an in-situ photodiode to collect the light intensity signal and applied the Absolute Limits algorithm followed by an image processing method to detect porosity, with an accuracy of $70.14 \pm 2.24\%$ for lack of fusion pores and $72.82 \pm 1.39\%$ for defects induced with higher laser power. However, there is still a need for research to reliably correlate the acquired signals to actual defects in the final part, as anomalies during the process may be modified by successive layers of material deposition and may overlap with nearby tracks if the melt pool width is larger than the hatch space, resulting in defects that evolve over time and space in terms of morphology, composition, and other factors. Additionally, it can be challenging to accurately compare in-process and post-process data due to after-build shrinkage and/or deformations, which can affect the accuracy of the comparison. Therefore, there is a need to research further how to interpret the data collected by in-process monitoring systems and how to use it to improve the LPBF process and the quality of the final parts.

In this study, in-process monitoring signals were collected using a single, spatially-integrated sensor, an indium gallium arsenide (InGaAs) photodiode, which was mounted coaxially to the laser path and measured radiation within a field of view centered on the melt pool in the near/short infrared range. The aim was to correlate these monitoring signals with internal pores measured by X-CT in order to train classifiers that can predict the presence and location of porosities while taking into account the inter-hatch effect. This "many-to-one" dataset preparation approach also helps to mitigate misalignment between in-process and post-process data.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 In-process monitoring setup

The LPBF machine was developed in-house by K.U. Leuven (LMQ) is equipped with a coaxial melt pool monitoring system. The system configuration was initially introduced by Mercelis et al.[11] and subsequently developed and improved by Craeghs, Clijsters, Buls, and Goossens et al.[9,12–14]. A CMOS camera and a photodiode are mounted coaxially to the optical path of the laser beam, as shown in Figure 1. The machine is equipped with a nLight Ytterbium (Yb) continuous wave fiber laser source with a wavelength of 1080 nm and maximum output power of 1 kW. The laser source is collimated (d) and subsequently positioned and focused on the powder bed using a Scanlab Varioscan (b). A melt pool is formed when the laser hits the powder in the workspace (a). According to the black-body radiation theory (Planck's law), a radiation spectrum is emitted based on the object's temperature. Part of the melt pool radiation is transmitted back through the varioscan (b) and is then reflected by a reflective thin-film interference filter, with a cut-off wavelength of 950 nm (c). A beam splitter (e) distributes the radiation evenly between a silicon photodiode (f) [15] and a CMOS camera (g) [16]. The photodiode captures the radiated intensity between 200-1000 nm wavelength. Due to the photodiode's high sensitivity, ambient light is filtered out using a band-pass filter, transparent only for the near-infrared (NIR) wavelength range between 800 and 950 nm, to observe only the melt pool radiation. The analogy signal from the photodiode (f) is sampled at 20 kHz and passed to the A/D converter with a 16-bit resolution (-10, 10v). The photodiode signal is synchronized and logged with the focal spot position. The actual monitoring experiment setup and results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Schematic of the in-process monitoring setup for LPBF

Figure 2: Experiment setup: a) LPBF process; b) In-process coaxial monitoring setup [1]; c) Monitoring signal

2.2 Experiment design and quality inspection

The research object presented here is a dense cuboid part. The process parameters are shown in Table 1. The layer thickness is 30 μm , and the hatch space is 70 μm . The scan strategy is contour first, with a bi-directional infill and a rotation of 90 degrees between layers. Thus, for one scan layer, there are 145 scan tracks and 200 data points for one track.

Table 1 L-PBF process parameters

Material	Powder particle size (μm)	Part dimensions (mm*mm*mm)	Powder P (W)	Scan speed v (mm/s)	Hatch space d (mm)	Layer thickness t (mm)
TC4 Grade 23	15-45	10*10*5	170	1000	0.07	0.03

The light intensity signals collected by the photodiode need to be labeled with the interior quality attributes, such as the size and location of pores and porosity ratio. An X-CT scan was performed on the LPBF parts to study the porosity distribution, as shown in Figure 3. The CT machine is Nikon XT H 225 ST with a multi-material target and a maximum tube potential of 225 kV. The scanning parameters are shown in Table 2. The magnification factor is 20, which leads to a resolution (voxel size) of 10 μm . The Feldkamp-Davis-Kress (FDK) algorithm is used to reconstruct volume from projections.

Table 2 X-CT scanning parameters

Target	Filter	Tube voltage (kV)	Tube power (W)	Exposure time (ms)	radiographs	Voxel size (μm)
Tungsten	1 mm thickness copper	180	12.1	2000	3600	10

The VGStudio MAX 2022.1 software was utilized to perform surface determination [17] using histogram analysis, which converts voxel data into 3D surface data and identifies the threshold value (iso-value) between the peaks of interest. Three planes were fitted to align with the world coordinate system by selecting points on these surfaces, and the object's coordinate system was registered using the 3-2-1 registration option. Porosity analysis was then carried out using VGDefX with a 0.7 interpolation factor for the threshold of surface determination, applying filters for volumes larger than 8 voxels and equivalent diameters smaller than 3 mm. Subsequent to this, slices with a height of 10 μm were exported with pores marked in black, and these images were batch processed in MATLAB for filtering, grayscale conversion, and binarization. In order to account for the layer thickness of 30 μm, the resulting images were stacked using the Boolean OR operation, resulting in a 1000*1000 pixel binary image with pores marked in white.

Figure 3: The X-CT scanning, porosity analysis, and volume layering.

2.3 Preprocessing photodiode signal and X-CT slice

The photodiode signals from layer 135 to layer 164 (corresponding to the part height between 4.08 mm and 4.95 mm) are used for model training, validating, and testing, as shown in Figure 4. Considering that pores may exist in more than one layer, if the training dataset and testing dataset are randomly split, it is possible to assign the cross-section of the same pore in different layers to the training set and the testing set. Such training and testing datasets are very close, making the testing set lose objectivity. Therefore, three layers are chosen as the gap between training and testing datasets.

Figure 4: Layer distribution for the training dataset and testing dataset.

One layer's photodiode is interpolated along the scanning and offset directions, finally obtaining a 1000*1000 matrix with one element equal to 10 μm. Therefore, the photodiode signals and X-CT images have the same resolution. To further model the inter-hatch effect, the value of the interpolation point equals the closest measured photodiode signal during the interpolation. This is the same as assuming each melt pool as a circle centered in the measured photodiode signal. Then the overlap hatching space region is dominant by the closest melt pool. Next, the signal matrix and X-CT slice are cropped using the same window

sizes, as shown in Figure 5. These sub-matrix and sub-images make up the dataset and correspond to each other. If the pore area in one sub-image exceeds the threshold, the label for the photodiode sub-matrice in the same position will be marked as 1.

Figure 5: Preprocessing photodiode signal and X-CT slice

According to work by Thanki et al. [18], the average width of the melt pool generated using the parameters in Table 1 is 179.2 μm ($12.8 \times 14 \mu\text{m}$). Due to the size of one pixel being 10 μm , the minimum window size is set as 20 pixels. However, the choice of window size, i.e., data points to train the CNN-LSTM network, is related to the melt pool physics and determines the spatial resolution of the monitoring method. A detailed description of the training dataset is discussed in Table 3.

Table 3 Pores/non-pores distribution for the training dataset

Dataset	Category	Window size			
		50*50	40*40	30*30	20*20
Training	Pores	197	174	192	178
	Non-Pores	7363	11638	20390	47072
Validating	Pores	25	21	22	19
	Non-Pores	815	1292	2265	5231
Testing	Pores	54	61	54	58
	Non-Pores	2346	3689	6480	14942

The procedure for analyzing these four window sizes is consistent, with a window size of 50*50 pixels used as an example. To prevent bias, the data representing pores were oversampled in the training dataset to balance the ratio of pores to non-pore samples, which was approximately 1:37. The input data formats required for various ML and DL models differ significantly. Three feature engineering techniques were applied to the photodiode signal to extract physical statistics, time-frequency spectrograms, and instantaneous frequency/spectrum entropy.

3 Experiment results

3.1 Performace for the dataset with a window size of 50*50

The proposed approach concerns a region-based comparison instead of an individual voxel-to-voxel comparison. This enables dealing with the inherent challenges of registration of in-line monitoring signals and X-CT voxel models, due to misalignments and manufacturing/thermal deformations. Moreover, it is known that nearby scan tracks can affect subsequent scan tracks through thermal conduction or spatter emission. It is better to consider one region instead of one voxel. The preprepared dataset were divided into two separate datasets: one for the training and another for the testing. The windowing operation crops the photodiode signal and X-CT slice of each printing layer into small square regions, which is a good practice for considering the

thermal impact in the region. Decreasing cropping window sizes can determine the minimum number of scan lines affected and increase the spatial resolution. Besides, due to the lack of LPBF physical modeling with high fidelity and high efficiency, it is challenging to use the physics-based pores prediction method. Thus, data-driven models serve as a solution. Different models with various inputs are trained, and the performance of the models is compared based on metrics. The models to be compared are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Data-driven models to be compared

Inputs	Models	Note
Feature engineering 1 + labels	Logistical Regression (L.R.)	1)
	Support Vector Machines (SVM)	
	Decision Tree (D.T.)	
	Neural Network (N.N.)	
	Naive Bayes (N.B.)	
Feature engineering 2 + labels	Alexnet + LR	2)
	Alexnet + LSTM	
Feature engineering 3 + labels	Bidirectional LSTM	3)
Sub-images + labels	MLP	4)
	Lenet	
	Alexnet	
	VGG	
	Resnet	

Furthermore, the Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curves for 1), 2), 3), and 4) are shown in Figure. 6. The four evaluation metrics are calculated, as listed in Table 5. We can get: (1) by combining domain knowledge, the Logistical Regression can achieve high classification performance with much less computation time; (2) by comparing input 1) and 3) with input 4), CNN can learn the features from data more effectively than manual feature engineering sometimes; (3) comprehensive performance of VGG 11 is the best with AUC reaching 0.86, the second-highest recall rate and F1 score.

Table 5: Model performance metrics for considering the inter-hatch effect.

Inputs	Models	AUC	Recall rate	F1 score	Accuracy
1)	LR	0.79	0.87	0.17	0.48
	SVM	0.5	0	0	0.77
	DT	0.53	0.1	0.1	0.73
	NN	0.61	0.74	0.09	0.7
	NB	0.75	0.72	0.18	0.53
2)	Alexnet+LR	0.58	0.31	0.13	0.83
	Alexnet+LSTM	0.74	0.56	0.29	0.89
3)	BiLSTM	0.72	0.6	0.23	0.62
4)	MLP	0.76	0.62	0.25	0.81
	Lenet	0.77	0.63	0.20	0.74
	Alexnet	0.72	0.51	0.26	0.85
	VGG11	0.86	0.68	0.31	0.84
	Resnet18	0.85	0.86	0.23	0.70

Figure 6: ROC curves for considering the inter-hatch effect

3.2 Changing dataset configuration

Modifying the dataset configuration by using different window sizes can impact the generalization performance of the model. Larger window sizes may lead to an improvement in performance due to the inclusion of more melt pools in a single sample, as well as the training of more robust filters that overlap with the transition regions between hatches. The AUC, which measures the ability to distinguish between pores and non-pores samples, increased by 8.9% when the window size was increased from 20*20 to 50*50. However, this change also resulted in a decrease in the model resolution, or the input image size, by a factor of 6.25. Therefore, there is a trade-off between model resolution and model accuracy, and it is important to consider both factors when determining the optimal window size for the dataset configuration.

Figure 7: Performance evaluation across different window sizes

When the threshold is set to 0.5, it is possible to examine more detailed metrics, such as the F1 score, recall rate, and the associated confusion matrix, as shown in Figure 8. The F1 score is a useful metric for analyzing imbalanced datasets, as it combines recall rate and precision. Also, in the context of anomaly detection, the recall rate is also important. The model trained on the 50*50 window size dataset was able to detect 68% of internal pores, but also had a 5% false positive rate. Comparing the window size of 40*40 to 30*30, the F1 score improved by 16% while the recall rate decreased by 5%. This indicates that the classifier trained on the larger window size is better at detecting negative samples, resulting in higher precision.

Figure 8: Confusion matrix for window size: a) 20*20; b) 30*30; c) 40*40; d) 50*50

4....Conclusions and future work

The purpose of this paper is to establish an ML model for correlating the results of real-time LPBF process monitoring with internal porosities detected using X-CT post-process measurements. X-CT serves not only as a method for detecting defects, but also as a crucial tool for verifying and improving in-process monitoring systems in the context of metal additive manufacturing. This methodology is expected to contribute to AM of high-quality parts in one go.

By comparing the photodiode signal of the monitoring system with pores obtained using X-CT, the ability of the ML models to accurately detect major geometrical defects was evaluated, as well as its current limitations, such as differences attributed to deformations and shrinkage that occur during the cool-down phase due to residual stresses. In the preliminary experiments described in this work, the system was able to correctly identify 68% of the actual internal porosities while also detecting 5% of false positives.

One potential avenue for future research is to use the ML in conjunction with X-CT post-process measurements to enhance in-process monitoring and active process control. Additionally, considering physics that happen in the building process may be worth investigating as a means of reducing false positives and improving defect detection rates, and the results obtained through this approach can be compared to those obtained using XCT post-process measurements.

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References

[1] L.R. Goossens, Advancements in Laser-Powder Bed Fusion: A Study on Machine, Process and In-Situ Monitoring Technology, (2021).

- [2] S.M. Thompson, L. Bian, N. Shamsaei, A. Yadollahi, An overview of Direct Laser Deposition for additive manufacturing; Part I: Transport phenomena, modeling and diagnostics, *Addit. Manuf.* 8 (2015) 36–62.
- [3] J.-P. Kruth, P. Mercelis, J. Van Vaerenbergh, T. Craeghs, Feedback control of selective laser melting, in: *Proc. 3rd Int. Conf. Adv. Res. Virtual Rapid Prototyp.*, TAYLOR & FRANCIS LTD, 2007: pp. 521–527.
- [4] B.K. Foster, E.W. Reutzel, A.R. Nassar, B.T. Hall, S.W. Brown, C.J. Dickman, Optical, Layerwise Monitoring of Powder Bed Fusion, in: *University of Texas at Austin*, 2015.
- [5] S. Coeck, M. Bisht, J. Plas, F. Verbist, Prediction of lack of fusion porosity in selective laser melting based on melt pool monitoring data, *Addit. Manuf.* 25 (2019) 347–356.
- [6] D. Kouprianoff, I. Yadroitsava, A. du Plessis, N. Luwes, I. Yadroitsev, Monitoring of Laser Powder Bed Fusion by Acoustic Emission: Investigation of Single Tracks and Layers, *Front. Mech. Eng.* 7 (2021).
- [7] L. Scime, J. Beuth, Anomaly detection and classification in a laser powder bed additive manufacturing process using a trained computer vision algorithm, *Addit. Manuf.* 19 (2018) 114–126.
- [8] L. Scime, D. Siddel, S. Baird, V. Paquit, Layer-wise anomaly detection and classification for powder bed additive manufacturing processes: A machine-agnostic algorithm for real-time pixel-wise semantic segmentation, *Addit. Manuf.* 36 (2020) 101453.
- [9] S. Clijsters, T. Craeghs, S. Buls, K. Kempen, J.-P. Kruth, In situ quality control of the selective laser melting process using a high-speed, real-time melt pool monitoring system, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 75 (2014) 1089–1101.
- [10] K. Taherkhani, E. Sheydaei, C. Eisner, M. Otto, E. Toyserkani, Development of a defect-detection platform using photodiode signals collected from the melt pool of laser powder-bed fusion, *Addit. Manuf.* 46 (2021) 102152.
- [11] P. Mercelis, J.-P. Kruth, Control of selective laser sintering and selective laser melting processes, 2007.
- [12] L.R. Goossens, B. Van Hooreweder, A virtual sensing approach for monitoring melt-pool dimensions using high speed coaxial imaging during laser powder bed fusion of metals, *Addit. Manuf.* 40 (2021) 101923.
- [13] S. Buls, S. Clijsters, J.-P. Kruth, Homogenizing the melt pool intensity distribution in the SLM process through system identification and feedback control, in: *Solid Free. Fabr. Symp.*, 2014: pp. 6–11.
- [14] T. Craeghs, F. Bechmann, S. Berumen, J.-P. Kruth, Feedback control of Layerwise Laser Melting using optical sensors, *Phys. Procedia.* 5 (2010) 505–514.
- [15] Thorlabs, Si Switchable Gain Detector User Guide, (2017).
- [16] Mikrotron GmbH, High-Speed CMOS CameraEoSens® 3CL Datasheet, (2016).
- [17] VGStudio MAX 3.2 software, <https://www.volumegraphics.com/en/products/vgstudio-max.html>, (n.d.).
- [18] A. Thanki, L. Goossens, A.P. Ompusunggu, M. Bayat, A. Bey-Temsamani, B. Van Hooreweder, J.-P. Kruth, A. Witvrouw, Melt pool feature analysis using a high-speed coaxial monitoring system for laser powder bed fusion of Ti-6Al-4V grade 23, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 120 (2022) 6497–6514.